

Deliverable 1.6

Practice Abstracts – batch 1

Fanny Tran (HUTTON)

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Contents

Deliverable Description & Contributors.....	2
Contents.....	3
Background to the LegumES project.....	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Practice Abstracts – Batch 1	5
2.1. Safe-guarding pea and field bean growth and yield: quantifying rhizobia in field soils	6
2.2. Climate impacts on protein production: Building resilience through low-input winter- or spring-sown pulse-based mixtures.....	8
2.3. Intercropping with barley to improve winter pea production	10
2.4. Rediscovering legumes as functional crops in cropping systems	13
2.5. Autumn-Sown Organically Managed Faba Bean-Oat Intercrops to enhance Crop Resilience.....	15

Background to the LegumES project

The legumES will ensure:

1. the uptake of best practices in agrobiodiverse legume-based cropped systems;
2. the uptake of methodologies and tools to quantify and balance the environmental and economic ecosystem service (ES) benefits provided by legumes;
3. that the ES benefits and cost offered by legumes are quantified across scales from field, farm, regional, national, and global levels; and
4. ES will be assessed to identify those conditions which are able to meet the EU targets: to decrease agrichemical inputs and losses, combat climate change, reverse biodiversity loss, and ensure the best nutritional provisioning.

To achieve this, legumES offers a multi-disciplinary consortium comprising 22 partners from 12 EU- and third countries (UK, CH) and including: 7, academic institutions; 6, Research and Technology Organizations; 5, SMEs (or micro-SMEs); 2, non-governmental organisations; and 2, large commercial companies. The individuals comprising legumES offer skills which include: agricultural-crop and -environment (ES) monitoring, life cycle assessment, economic- and socioeconomic-modelling, social-science, EU-agricultural and environmental policy, and law, plus decision support systems. The legumES research and innovation strategy centres on the use of a multiactor action-research approach, that is, where legume-facing stakeholders, and especially producers though all value chains actors, can 'operate', 'collaborate' and, 'reflect critically' on the measured ES benefits and costs of legume-based cropped systems, including legumes use in marginal lands; so that an optimal balance of ES can be achieved with success locally, and globally. To help achieve this, LegumES also centres activities on a suite of 25 innovative legume-based Pilot Studies which use a wide range of legume species and types, plus different cropping approaches and linked value chains spanning the pedoclimatic regions of Europe.

For more information on the project, see:

- [Valorising and balancing the ecosystem service benefits offered by legumes, and legume-based cropped systems | LegumES | Project | Fact sheet | HORIZON | CORDIS | European Commission](#)
- www.legumES-project.eu

1. Introduction

Practice abstracts (PAs) are concise summaries designed to share innovative, practice-oriented solutions with farmers, foresters, advisors, and rural communities. Under the EIP-AGRI framework, Operational Groups and Horizon projects collaborate to stimulate knowledge exchange and disseminate results across the EU. These abstracts follow the EIP-AGRI common format, ensuring harmonized and easily understandable communication of project outcomes. By fostering knowledge flows and connecting project partners with practitioners, practice abstracts address real needs from the field, support the development of valuable project proposals, and facilitate networking. This approach helps avoid duplication of efforts and promotes the adoption of good practices and innovative solutions throughout the agricultural sector.

This legumES' deliverable report features five PAs, written by four different project partners (Table 1). The PAs cover a range of practices from quantifying rhizobia to intercropping to improve winter pea production. These PAs have also been published on the EU CAP Network website ([Valorising and balancing the ecosystem service benefits offered by legumes, and legume-based cropped systems | EU CAP Network](#)) and Zenodo legumES community ([Search legumES: valorising the ecosystem benefits of legumes](#)).

Table 1. List of Practice Abstracts prepared by LegumES partners.

No	Title	Partner	Country
1	Safe-guarding pea and field bean growth and yield: quantifying rhizobia in field soils	HUTTON/UCP	UK/PT
2	Climate impacts on protein production: Building resilience through low-input winter- or spring-sown pulse-based mixtures	HUTTON/UCP	UK/PT
3	Intercropping with barley to improve winter pea production	HUTTON	UK
4	Rediscovering legumes as functional crops in cropping systems	UNIPG	IT
5	Autumn-Sown Organically Managed Faba Bean-Oat Intercrops to enhance Crop Resilience	FIBL	CH

As the project progresses and Pilot Studies work programme starts to be implemented, more practice abstracts will be produced. These include 'How to measure on field indicators for Ecosystem services', 'adopting precision agriculture in legume-based farming systems' and 'how to choose the best species for crop association with grain legumes'.

2. Practice Abstracts – Batch 1

Safe-guarding pea and field bean growth and yield: quantifying rhizobia in field soils

Problem

Poor growth and so yield of pulse crops such as pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) and field bean (*Vicia faba* L.) due to low levels of root nodulation as a function of low rhizobia numbers in soil.

Solution

Application of a molecular diagnostic method can quantify the number of pea- and bean-rhizobia in soil; with low population numbers indicating a limitation to crop performance and yield.

Benefits

With the number of rhizobia in-soil known, this potentially yield-limiting factor can be identified or excluded. If rhizobia numbers are low, high-performing (elite) rhizobia from commercial sources should be applied to seed before sowing.

Applicability box

Theme

Pulse crop performance and yield protection.

Keywords

Crop growth; yield; rhizobia; molecular diagnostics; elite rhizobia.

Context

Wherever peas and beans are grown in-field.

Required time

Molecular Diagnostics: allow 2 months.
Elite rhizobia application: allow 2 weeks (for delivery); seed inoculation is rapid (1-2h)

Period of impact

Within 4 weeks improved root nodulation and seedling growth should be apparent.

Specialist Equipment: Not necessary on farm.

Best in: any cropped system type.

Practical recommendation

- Molecular diagnostics demands specific equipment, and expertise, and need carried out by professional service providers including: the Processors and Growers Research Organisation (Roger Vickers; roger@pgro.org); and/or the James Hutton Institute (pete.iannetta@hutton.ac.uk).
- If rhizobia numbers are low a relatively low-cost remedy (even without the molecular diagnostic test), is the application of high performing ('elite') rhizobia to seed before sowing.

- Elite rhizobia should be purchased from high quality commercial providers e.g., Legume Technology Ltd, www.legumetechnology.co.uk.

An illustrative graph showing the potential relationship between bean yield and abundance of soil rhizobia. Noting low yield is not always due to low rhizobia numbers, as other factors may be important too.

Further Reading

Maluk et al., (2021). Fields with no recent legume cultivation have sufficient nitrogen-fixing rhizobia for crops of faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.). *Plant and Soil*, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-021-05246-8>.

Macdonald et al., (2011). Development of a real-time PCR assay for detection and quantification of *Rhizobium leguminosarum* bacteria and discrimination between different biovars in zinc-contaminated soil. *Applied and environmental microbiology* **77**, 4626-4633. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.02232-10>.

About this practice abstracts

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Visit: [Safe-guarding pea and field bean growth and yield: quantifying rhizobia in field soils](#)

Climate impacts on protein production: Building resilience through low-input winter- or spring-sown pulse-based mixtures.

Problem

Climate change impacts is causing unpredictable and extreme weather across Europe. Assuring protein yield potential demands adaptive cropping strategies

Solution

To use winter- and spring-sown mixtures, harvested either as grain or whole crop (silage) - depending on the climatic effects experienced.

Benefits

Protein yield is safeguarded using whole-crop, when grain yields may be compromised., although use of whole-crop may be limited to consumptions by ruminants. Benefits are therefore easier to realise in mixed farming systems (e.g., which include cows, and sheep); and/or where whole crop 'biorefining' is used.

Applicability box

Theme

Protein yield resilience.

Keywords

Protein; yield; resilience; grain; whole-crop.

Context

Arable and mixed-farm systems.

Required time

Growing season, whether spring- or winter-sown mixtures.

Period of impact

On growing season, post-harvest and post-harvest seed or whole-crop preparation.

Specialist Equipment: Not necessary.

Best used in: Cropped systems affected by a limited growing season, due to climate change impacts.

Practical recommendation

- High protein yields were obtained using either:
 - winter-sown faba (field) bean and wheat harvested as whole-crops; or,
 - spring-sown pea and wheat harvested as grain.
- The protein yields were up to 2x that achieved by average monocrops.
- Highest protein yields were obtained without synthetic nitrogen fertiliser use (50 kg/ha avoided).

The table below provides species, varietal and yield data for the top performing crop-mixtures.

Sown Crop-types, Species (Cultivars)	Total Yield / Protein Yield (t/ha) Yield type, biomass, (Protein t/ha, %)	Crop-Mixture Options			Fertiliser use (50 kg N/ha)
		Pea	Faba	Wheat	
Winter-faba bean & -wheat (Tundra, or Pantani & Skyscraper)	Whole Crop, 12-15 (1.2-1.9, 13 %)	No	Yes	Yes	No
Spring-pea & -wheat (Orchestra & WPB Escape) (faba = cv. Yukon)	Grain, 8-10 (1.7-1.9, 19 %)	Yes	(Yes)	Yes	No

For comparison: grain protein yields of monocrops, estimated from UK yield averages (@15% moisture):
 - **faba bean:** winter, or spring-sown, yield 3.6/3.5 t/ha (respectively), @28% protein = **0.85 t/ha** (dry weight)
 - **pea:** spring-sown, yield 3.2 t/ha, @22.5 % protein = **0.61 t/ha** (dry weight)
 - **wheat:** winter/spring, yield 5.7/9.0 t/ha, @12.5 % protein = **0.96 t/ha** (dry weight)

Options in brackets were not found to be essential for protein yield resilience.
Fertiliser weight of nitrogen (N) from avoided use of ammonium nitrate.

1

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About this practice abstracts

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Intercropping with barley to improve winter pea production

Problem

Intercropping winter peas with barley could prevent legume canopy collapse and competition from weeds. There is limited knowledge, however, of the sowing ratios and agronomy that improve performance of winter pea-barley intercrops in Scotland.

Solution

We trialled multiple winter pea and barley cultivars in different sowing densities and ratios, soil cultivation, fertiliser and other inputs to detect the best outcomes for yield, weed and pest control.

Benefits

Highest grain yields and lowest weed cover were achieved with sowing densities of 1.25x standard densities (pea+barley), >50% std. density barley in the mix, and 75% of the standard nitrogen level for barley, indicating potential costs and benefits when maximizing winter pea performance.

Practical recommendations

- In Northern UK, winter legume-cereal crops can be sown within a suitable weather window in the autumn (September – November).
- Crops can be sown into ploughed or unploughed soil, although yields tend to be lower with direct drilled crops.
- Select varieties that are more likely to coincide in their maturity timings, using information from industry recommended lists of crop varieties.
- Winter survival and competitiveness of the main commercial pea varieties can be problematic but novel germplasm selected for intercropping offers improvements in future.
- Highest grain yields and lowest weed cover can be achieved with sowing densities of 1.25x standard densities (pea+barley), and 75% of the standard nitrogen level for barley (**Figure 1**).

Applicability box

Theme

Agronomy of legume-based intercrops

Keywords

Winter pea, winter barley, sowing density, ratio, nitrogen fertiliser, cultivation

Context

Scotland, rest of the UK

Application time

Autumn (sowing) to summer (harvest)

Required time

An annual crop growing season

Period of impact

An annual growing season

Equipment

Drills and combines capable of handling cereal and legume seeds and crops together, and grain separators

Best in

Arable cropping

Winter pea-barley crop trialled at the James Hutton Institute (Alison Karley).

Figure 1. Grain yield of pea+barley from a standard plot (6 m²) averaged across three years of field trials (nine in total) in Scotland, UK. Average yield varied in response to total intercrop sowing density (left – as a proportion of standard monocrop sowing density) and nitrogen fertiliser input level (right – as a percentage of standard winter barley N fertiliser levels).

- Pre-emergence herbicide reduces early weed competition but is rarely needed after crop establishment; protection of the pea crop against bird damage can be important for crop establishment.
- Split fertiliser treatments are applied at sowing (Sept-Nov) and during barley tillering (March-May), at 50-75% of the standard nitrogen rate for barley.
- Monitor crop development, and pest and disease incidence, although the latter was low in our 3 years of trials.
- Crops are combine harvested in late summer (Aug-Sept); desiccation might be needed prior to harvest if pea and barley do not converge in maturity timing.
- Pea and barley grain can be separated after harvest, depending on access to grain drying, storage and separating facilities.

Further information

Video

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jIB79tr2pXA&t=4s>

Weblinks

For more practical recommendations, see:

- <https://www.arablescotland.org.uk/virtual-event-2020>
- <https://www.arablescotland.org.uk/virtual-event-2021>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KLwdlpzFRm8>

About this practice abstract

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Rediscovering legumes as functional crops in cropping systems

Problem

Legumes are often regarded as non-profitable crops due to their lower and highly volatile yield, due to pests and weed control.

Solution

Introducing legumes as part of a crop-rotation can supply a variety of benefits called “ecosystem services”; which could be more accurately quantified by assessing the legume impact over the whole crop rotation, rather than just as a single crop.

Benefits

Legumes in crop-rotation systems provide a suite of ecosystem benefits, including improvements in crop diversification, encouraging natural nutrient cycling, reducing pollution, and supporting pollinating, and other beneficial insects.

Applicability box

Theme

Ecosystem services provision

Keywords

Ecosystem service benefits; legumes; cover crops;

Context

Europe

Application time

Throughout the year

Required time At least several months, depending on the specific practice.

Period of impact

Throughout the season and in the following seasons.

Equipment

Standard farm equipment.

Best in

Any cropping systems

Practical recommendation

Use leguminous main crops and cover crops as a:

- ‘green manure’ prior to high nitrogen (N)-fertiliser demanding crops (Figure 1a);
- sacrificial green manure, grown then mown between cash-crop (cereal) rows (Figure 1b); and,
- prior to high nitrogen (N) fertiliser demanding crops (Figure 1c).

Figure 1. A. Triticale -hairy vetch winter cover crops to control soil erosion, nitrate leaching and increasing N availability in the soil; B. Temporary cropping with chickpea, lupin and hairy vetch to increase nutrient supply in durum wheat; and C. Pea and faba bean in pea-wheat-chickpea-wheat rotation and in a faba bean-wheat rotation to increase nutrient supply to wheat.

About this practice abstract

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Autumn-Sown Organically Managed Faba Bean-Oat Intercrops to enhance Crop Resilience

Problem

In organic faba beans cultivation success is often determined by two main factors: effective weed management; and limiting the impact of diseases.

Solution

According to experience in the Swiss pedoclimate, intercropping faba beans with oats (Figure 1) can increase yield resilience for winter- and spring-sown crops. This is achieved through the ability of intercrops to reduce weed and pest pressure. The total yield also tends to be higher with mixed crops compared to monocrops; since both oats and beans are harvested (together).

Benefits

In this intercrop, oats quickly germinate to establish soil cover, reducing (late) weed growth; and reducing aphid numbers, which also serve as virus vectors. Oats has a more 'neutral' impact environmentally on the crop rotation compared to other cereal crops; better suppressing weeds; even when mechanical weed control (harrowing) is not possible due to unfavourable conditions. Also, if other (cereal) crop fail, oats can compensate for this loss.

Applicability box

Theme

Intercropping Legumes and Cereal.

Keywords

Intercropping; Faba Beans; Oats; Yield Resilience; Organic Agriculture.

Context

Central Europe.

Application time

Autumn/Spring sowing

Period of impact

Cultivation period; and across whole crop rotation.

Equipment

Standard equipment; capability to weigh/mix oat & bean seed.

Best in

Organic agriculture.

Figure 1. Left: Autumn sown faba beans with oats, harrow in the background and Right: Spring sown faba beans with oats. Photos: Matthias Klais, FiBL.

Practical recommendation

- **Seed mix:** a good mix to start is 80-90 % of faba beans, and 30-40 % Oats. % = of usual monocrops stand density.
- **Sowing seed mix** at 12 cm row distance, seeding depth 3-4 cm, 4-5 cm in sandy soil. (This is for Switzerland; and needs optimised for other countries/regions).

- **Synthetic nitrogen (N) fertiliser** is not required to facilitate production/N accumulation (by legume crop).
- **Autumn-sown oats and beans will ripen at the same time.** Spring-sowing requires late-maturing oat varieties for simultaneous ripening with the faba bean.
- **Oats N-content may be reduced** (compared to monocropped oats), due to limited N-fertiliser use.
- **The combine harvester needs adjusted** to harvest the main cash crop, i.e., faba bean.
- **The proportion of legumes in the harvest can vary** (averaged between 50-60 % over the years, with large fluctuations). The proportion of oats needs optimised for your conditions by experience.

Further information

Further reading

- <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/32816/1/1670-koernerleguminosen-mischkulturen.pdf>
- <https://www.agrarforschungschweiz.ch/2015/11/mit-mischkulturen-die-inlaendische-eiweissversorgung-verbessern/>

Weblinks

- <https://www.bioaktuell.ch/pflanzenbau/ackerbau/mischkulturen>
- <https://www.lko.at/media.php?filename=download%3D%2F2020.02.11%2F1581422570268322.pdf&rn=Nanoviren%20-%20Ertragsausf%C3%A4lle%20bei%20Leguminosen.pdf>

About this practice abstract

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Visit: [Autumn-Sown Organically Managed Faba Bean-Oat Intercrops to enhance Crop Resilience](#)

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